

SHORT COMMUNICATION

DEFECATION RATE OF EASTERN COTTONTAIL (*SYLVILAGUS FLORIDANUS*) AND EUROPEAN BROWN HARE (*LEPUS EUROPAEUS*)

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Abstract

Pellet count techniques are a useful tool to assess the density of many mammal species, such as European brown hare (*Lepus europaeus*) and Eastern cottontail (*Sylvilagus floridanus*). Different methods have been developed, some of them accounting for the decay rate of pellets in the study area, nevertheless all of them require the estimated number of droppings produced through time by the single individual, the “defecation rate”. Despite this, very few papers define such value for the two species. Daily droppings produced by five caged individuals of Eastern Cottontail were collected from November 2013 to March 2014 and the daily number of pellets produced by four couples of caged European Brown Hare was estimated from March to October 2013. The effect of environmental temperature on the production of pellet was measured, as temperature plays a role in the defecation rate of European rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*). A defecation rate of 485.9 ± 34.05 pellets per day was estimated for Eastern cottontail, whereas a value of 394.9 ± 16.94 pellets per day was estimated for European brown hare. Environmental temperature did not seem to influence the production of faecal pellets. The estimated daily production of pellets reported in this work can be used as a reference value to assess the densities of the two species through pellet count surveys. Nevertheless it must be acknowledged that seasonal variations in such parameter may arise, due to environmental and physiological factors, and further experimental studies are needed to estimate their magnitude and their effect on estimated densities.

Introduction

The European brown hare (*Lepus europaeus*) and the Eastern cottontail (*Sylvilagus floridanus*) are two lagomorphs that coexist in many agricultural environments of Central and Northern Italy [1]. While the European hare is a major native game species,

the Eastern cottontail has being repeatedly introduced by hunters since 1960 [2] and local eradication plans have being disposed, due to its allochthonous nature and its potential role as a vector for the European Brown Hare Syndrome Virus (EBHSV) [3].

The two species are usually monitored by gamekeepers in hunting estates and in protected areas through spotlight counts performed in winter (December to March), in order to dispose a sustainable yield of hares and to test the effectiveness of culling for cottontails. Spotlight counts are usually a suitable tool to infer the densities of European hare, however in mountains and woody areas factors such as the vegetation and the terrain slope could hamper their effectiveness. Moreover cottontails often forage at night close to patches of permanent vegetation that can provide shelter and hinder detectability [4].

Indirect methods, like pellet count techniques [5,6] can therefore be adopted to monitor the two species in those situations where limited detectability negatively affects spotlight counts. Three pellet count estimate methods are currently available: droppings can be counted in a single sampling and corrected for their estimated persistence on the field (unclear plot method), otherwise they can be counted in two stages without accounting for their persistence (cleared plot method) [8] or they can be adjusted for pellet persistence by marking part of them and modelling their decay with an exponential function [7]. It must be noticed that all these techniques require to be corrected for defecation rates, in order to link the number of pellets counted at sampling plots with the number of individuals in the study area. However defecation rates cannot be measured during pellet counts and a general or bibliographic value is commonly adopted. The main approaches adopted in the past to assess this parameter included observing the production of droppings of free ranging individuals in their natural environment through focal sampling [9], counting the recruitment rate of pellets on the ground [8], or collecting the faecal pellets produced by caged individuals at regular intervals [10,11].

Many factors can affect the production of droppings in mammals, notably seasonal variations in the availability [11] or in the quality of food [10] and the metabolic rate, which is strongly dependent on individual size and environmental conditions such as temperature [14]. A previous experimental study conducted on the European rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) highlighted a negative correlation between the defecation rate and average environmental temperature [15]. Some authors have provided defecation rates for the European hare and the Eastern cottontail [7-13], nevertheless it must be noticed that the only existing scientific paper about European hare was performed in an alpine environment [9] and another published work [16] provided a mixed value for the European hare (*L. europaeus*) and the mountain hare (*L. timidus*).

Despite some indications about the defecation rate of hares can be found inside of some guidelines for mammal monitoring [7,12-13], these publications often do not provide any reference from scientific literature. Therefore the aim of this work is to measure the daily mean defecation rate of European hares and Eastern cottontails in a controlled environment, in order to enable researchers and field scientists to estimate the densities of the two species through pellet-count techniques. Moreover this paper aims to test whether the daily production of droppings is correlated to environmental temperature, as recorded in the European rabbit.

Methods

This work involved the collection of faecal pellets produced by caged individuals of European hare and Eastern cottontail. All the hares had been raised as breeders and during fieldwork they were held in captivity by two authorized gamekeepers to produce leverets for hunting estates. On the other hand all the individuals of Eastern cottontail which were involved in the experiment had been explicitly captured for this study. Wildlife trapping, handling and captivity were authorized by the Wildlife and Fishery Office of the Province of Pistoia, in accordance with the Italian law (National Law no. 157/92). Animals were not manipulated during sampling, as faecal pellets were collected from a shadow net for gardening placed under the cages and this allowed to reduce stress. The defecation rate was calculated as the daily number of pellets produced by any experimental unit in 24 hours, notably by any couple of hares or by any individual of Eastern cottontail. Therefore the defecation rates recorded for the European hare were averaged over two individuals of both sexes. It was decided to keep the breeders together, in order to avoid the potential stress deriving from their separation. Cottontails were placed in individual cages, to prevent aggressive behavior, as trapped individuals were not used to share the same space. However estimating differences in the defecation rates of the two sexes does not have any practical meaning, because these differences cannot be detected during pellet counts on the field. From March to August 2013 the faecal pellets produced by four couples of European hare were collected at two farms. The first two couples were reared in Gavinana (44°03'16.82"N 10°49'33.56"E, elevation = 850 m, Italy) and the other two in Pistoia (43°56'23.03"N 10°59'15.09" E, elevation= 65 m, Italy). Monitored couples had been previously placed in metal cages (180 x 80 x 125 cm) and were fed ad libitum with a diet based on a mix of commercial pellet food, alfalfa hay, local fresh vegetables and water. In the case of European hare environmental temperature was not experimentally manipulated, but recorded at two meteorological stations placed, respectively at 7.43 km from Gavinana and at 1 km from Pistoia, which had the same elevation and climatic conditions. The differences between the elevation values of the two sampling sites and the long timespan adopted for sampling ensured a wide range of temperatures (min=11°C, max=27°C). In order to link pellet production to specific daily temperatures faecal pellets of hares were collected every 24 hours, otherwise after a maximum timespan of 48 hours. When pellets were not collected for more than 48 hours, the shadow nets under the cages were cleaned and the collection of droppings was restarted. From October to November 2013, five individuals of Eastern cottontail were trapped with double entrance traps in a protected area in Spicchio (43°49'01.32"N 10°53'46.83"E, elevation = 45 m, Italy) and placed in individual rabbit cages (84x45x39 cm) at the School of Veterinary Medicine of the University of Pisa. There they were fed ad libitum with a diet based on a mix of commercial pellet food, alfalfa hay and water. In the case of cottontails, because measurements occurred in winter, from 26/11/2013 to 19/03/2014, environmental temperature was partially manipulated: after having been placed outside for 16 days (min=4.6 °C, max=7°C) individuals were moved into a room with artificial heating and aeration for 21 days at 20°C and for other 20 days at 30°C, then they were brought outside again for 56 days to be exposed at intermediate thermal values (min=8°C, max=13°C) (Table 2).

However, before being exposed to higher or lower temperatures caged individuals benefited from an acclimatization period of 3 days at intermediate values, to reduce likely physiological stress deriving from sudden thermic changes. Faecal pellets were collected every 24 hours or after a maximum timespan of 48 hours and their production was not recorded during the acclimatization period and the following week, to avoid any bias related to physiological changes. The normality of the data was checked with quantile analysis and the daily number of pellets was log-transformed to reduce heteroscedasticity. A linear regression was fit, using the logarithm of the daily number of pellet as the response variable and the environmental average daily temperature as a predictor. No random effect was introduced in the linear model to account for individual differences in the response variable, due to the experimental design, which was partially based on couples of individuals. Defecation rates were estimated as a mean value with a standard error, assuming a normal distribution of the number of faecal pellets produced in the 24 hours.

Results

Faecal pellets were collected from each couple of hares for, respectively, 24, 21, 16 and 12 days. Two cottontails died during the sampling and the individual production of droppings was measured for, respectively, 19, 26, 20, 10 an 16 days. The collection of faecal pellets from hares and cottontails was not performed each day and the distribution of sampling in each species was shown, respectively in Table 1 and in Table 2.

Table 1: Seasonal distribution of sampling for European brown hare (*L. europaeus*): number of days of fieldwork and average environmental temperature per month.

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
Sampling (days)	0	0	2	15	0	2	12	15	24	2	0	0
Average temperature (°C)	-	-	12.5	15.2	-	19.3	22.3	24.4	17.8	18.8	-	-

Table 2: Seasonal distribution of sampling for Eastern cottontail (*S. floridanus*): number of days of measurements and average temperature per block of days.

	Period			
	26/11/2013	13/12/2013	02/01/2014	23/01/2014
	-	-	-	-
	12/12/2013	02/01/2014	22/01/2014	19/03/2014
Sampling (days)	9	4	6	7
Average temperature (°C)	5.41	23.4	30	10.4

The defecation rate of European hare was estimated as 394.9 ± 16.94 (mean \pm s.e) pellets per day and the defecation rate of Eastern cottontail as 485.9 ± 34.05 (mean \pm s.e) pellets per day (Table 3). Environmental temperature was not a good predictor for the daily number of faecal pellets produced by the two species, as its correlation with such value was not significant, neither in European hare ($\beta = -0.006$; $p > 0.05$) nor in Eastern cottontail ($\beta = -0.001$, $p > 0.05$).

Table 3: Measured defecation rate of sampled units of Eastern cottontail (*S. floridanus*) and European brown hare (*L. europaeus*).

Species	Number of individuals per cage	Sampled days	Defecation rate		
			Individual mean	Individual standard deviation	Species-specific estimated defecation rate (mean \pm s.e)
<i>S.floridanus</i>	1	19	580.3	94.05	485.9 \pm 34.05
	1	26	454.5	140.48	
	1	10	484.9	192.28	
	1	20	518.9	194.96	
	1	16	384.2	145.15	
<i>L.europaeus</i>	2	24	418.9	58.48	394.9 \pm 16.94
	2	21	426.6	72.99	
	2	16	349.5	68.26	
	2	12	351.8	55.78	
	2	12	351.8	55.78	

Discussion

The defecation rate of Eastern cottontails was comparable to those reported in previous experiences with caged individuals, however in this case the experimental design, sample size and diet were clearly specified, whereas this did not always occur in the past [10]. The defecation rate of European hares was similar to that measured in a previous scientific work on free-ranging animals [9] and to other values reported in grey literature [12,13]. Nevertheless our measured defecation rate was much higher than the value of 100-150 pellets per day suggested by the UKBAP guidelines [7]. The defecation rates of the two species did not seem to vary across different temperatures, in contrast to what had been previously reported for the European rabbit [15]. However other parameters, which were not recorded in this experimental work, may interact with the production of pellets, like individual weight [15], water balance [19] and metabolic rates [14]. Further studies should address their role and interactions, as well as adopting Linear Mixed Modelling with random effects accounting for the random variation between individuals. This work can be regarded as a general reference for future pellet count assessments of the two target species, performed by technicians and researchers, as the estimated defecation rates of the two species generally agree with those reported in previous publications (Table 4). However all those who are interested in using them should also be aware of the fact that estimating defecation rates from animals in a controlled environment, which benefited from a constant and balanced diet and had a low and constant metabolism, could have led to smoothed values, excluding those sources of variability that exist in nature. The production of faecal pellets made by free-ranging lagomorphs could vary at certain times of the year due to seasonal variations in the quality of food [10] to reductions in its accessibility [11] or to parasite loads [17]. The role played by all these potential factors should be carefully tested, as their impact on defecation rates is still not well defined. As an example it has to be noticed that our defecation rate for hares, despite not having been measured in winter conditions, did not strongly differ from another one obtained by free-ranging individuals in an alpine environment where the terrain was covered by snow [9]. Recently it has been discovered that the Japanese hare (*Lepus brachyurus*) can also re-ingest its hard faeces: if this behavior occurred in other lagomorphs, it is likely that it would affect their defecation rates, as well as potentially introducing bias

in pellet count estimates by limiting the availability of dungs in the field [18]. Where hares coexists with cottontails, due to the similarity of the dungs of cottontails and leverets, density estimation with pellet count techniques should be performed from December to February only, to avoid any identification bias. Finally future studies should provide values of pellet persistence on the ground, allowing for comparisons between cleared and uncleared plot methods in Italian environments in order to develop a standardized method to perform large scale surveys of the two species, similarly to what has been done for the European rabbit [20].

Table 4: Defecation rate of Eastern cottontail (*S. floridanus*) and European brown hare (*L. europaeus*) reported in previous works.

Paper	Species	Sample size of the experiment (individuals)	Defecation rate
[10]	<i>S.floridanus</i>	4	450 ± 20
			505 ± 26
			496 ± 18
			514 ± 17
[9],[13]	<i>L.europaeus</i>	5	410 (min =296, max = 671)
[7]	<i>L.europaeus</i>	Unknown	100 - 150
[12]	<i>L.europaeus</i>	Unknown	400

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